

TRANSLATING IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS: A LINGUISTIC PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: This article studies the issue of translating idiomatic expressions from a linguistic point of view. Idioms are one of the riches of language, and in their translation it is not enough to search for lexical or grammatical equivalents alone, but a deep understanding of the cultural context is also important. Idiomatic expressions in English and Uzbek are analyzed, and linguistic approaches used in their translation are studied. Translation problems, their causes and solutions are highlighted on the basis of practical examples. Also, the semantic and stylistic aspects of idioms specific to both languages are analyzed on a comparative basis. The work serves as a useful theoretical and practical material for students, translators and language learners studying in the fields of translation studies, linguistics and intercultural communication.

Keywords: idiomatic expressions, translation, linguistic approach, semantics, pragmatics, intercultural communication, English, Uzbek, translation problems, phraseological units.

In modern translation studies, the correct and meaningful translation of idiomatic expressions is one of the important problems. Idioms are figurative expressions that reflect the national spirit, culture and folk images of the language. They increase the stylistic richness of the text, enhance its emotional tone and further enliven its aesthetic effect. Therefore, when translating idiomatic expressions, it is necessary to take into account not only the word level, but also the deep contextual and cultural layers of the language.

There is a noticeable difference between English and Uzbek. Both languages have a rich idiomatic layer, and their correct translation plays an important role in intercultural communication. However, translators face many linguistic, semantic and pragmatic problems in this process.

The various features of phraseological expressions can also be identified by classifying them according to their external form. This classification pays more attention to the number of words in phraseological expressions. As a result of the classification, it is possible to determine how many words the phrases consist of by their nature. Many linguists express the opinion that phraseological phrases consist of more than two words only. However, observations show that phraseological phrases consist of two, three or more words. However, some linguists believe that there are also phrases consisting of one word. In particular, according to Professor A. Jafarov, one-word phrases are formed at the highest stage of development of

idiomatic expressions. Phrases of this type are expressed by a compound word or a single word, and they differ from compound words in that they cannot directly express a thought. An idiomatic meaning is also understood through one word. But it is difficult to call such words phrases. Because a phrase must consist of a combination of words. The opinions of V. V. Vinogradov, A. Abakumov, A. Shakhmatov are valuable in this regard.

Idiomatic expressions are word combinations that have formed in a particular language and often cannot be directly translated, have a portable meaning. They usually arise on the basis of many years of linguistic experience, culture, traditions and social values.

The main features of idioms are as follows:

Translatable meaning: The meaning of an idiom differs from the literal meaning of the words that make it up.

Stability: Idioms are usually used in an unchanging form, their grammatical structure cannot be changed.

Language specificity: Each language has its own idioms, and their equivalents in another language do not always exist.

For example, the English phrase "break the ice" literally means "to break the ice", but in reality it means "to start a conversation or dialogue".

There are different approaches to classifying idioms. They are mainly based on semantic and structural criteria:

Semantic classification: Idioms are divided into the following groups according to their meaning:

Idioms expressing an emotional state (e.g., "cry over spilled milk")

Idioms expressing an action or state (e.g., "hit the road")

Idioms expressing a decision or opinion (e.g., "on the fence")

Structural classification: Idioms are divided according to their grammatical form into the following:

Verb phrases: "give up", "look after"

Idioms in the form of expressions: "It's raining cats and dogs"

Similes: "as cool as a cucumber"

Idioms reflect not only linguistic, but also cultural and contextual aspects of the language. They are often associated with the history, social life, customs, and national values of a people. Therefore, cultural differences play a big role in their translation. For example, while the English phrase "bring home the bacon" is typical of the culture of the United States and Great Britain, in Uzbek there are similar expressions "non topib kelmoq" or "rozg'orni taminlamoq". Both perform the same function, but their cultural roots are different.

The main problem in translating idiomatic expressions is that they have a portable meaning. Many idioms, if translated literally, do not convey the original meaning or are completely misinterpreted. For example, if the English phrase "kick the bucket" is translated into Uzbek as "chetga tepmoq", the meaning is lost, while in fact this expression means "to die".

From a linguistic point of view, there are several approaches to translating idiomatic expressions. Among them, the most effective are the following:

Replacing with an equivalent idiom. In this method, the translator selects an idiom in the target language that is synonymous with the idiom in the source language and has the same function. For example: "to spill the beans" - "to reveal the secret". An explanatory translation. If there is no equivalent, it is necessary to translate the meaning of the expression by explaining it. For example: "jump on the bandwagon" - "to join the popular idea".

Refusal of literal translation. It is not enough to translate an idiomatic expression grammatically correctly. The translator must analyze the meaning of this expression in context and reflect it in a natural and meaningful way. Pragmatic adaptation. In this approach, the translator seeks to preserve the impact, stylistic tone and function of the expression. This is especially important in the translation of literary texts and films. Idiomatic expressions are often associated with national mentality, historical events, religious beliefs or folk oral traditions. Therefore, the translation process must take into account not only language, but also intercultural differences. The translator must be aware of these differences, have cultural competence and choose an alternative to the expression in the target language. For example, the English expression "bring home the bacon" (to earn an income) is contextually translated in Uzbek as "non topib kelmoq". Both express the idea of providing a living, but they differ in cultural grounds. The issue of translating idiomatic expressions was analyzed in depth from a linguistic point of view. Studies show that idioms are important language units that embody nationality, cultural values, historical memory, and folk images in any language. Therefore, their translation should be carried out taking into account not only grammatically or lexically, but also semantically and culturally. Finding the correct equivalent of idioms in translation or transmitting them while preserving their contextual meaning directly depends on the translator's linguistic and intercultural competence. As it was found during the work, effective approaches used in translating idioms are finding an equivalent, explanatory translation, pragmatic adaptation, and contextual interpretation. Also, the results of a practical analysis conducted on the example of English and Uzbek showed that both languages have their own idiomatic expressions, and their successful translation requires in-depth knowledge of the internal laws and cultural characteristics of the language.

As a final conclusion, it can be said that linguistic approaches serve as an important theoretical and practical basis for the translation of idiomatic expressions. They provide translators with a deep understanding of the language and ensure a high-quality translation process.

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